

EASY WAYS OF MAKING PARAGRAPHS IN ENGLISH
INGLIZ TILIDA PARAGRAPH TUZISHNI OSON USULLARI
ЛЕГКИЕ СПОСОБЫ СОЗДАНИЕ АБЗАЦА ПО-АНГЛИЙСКИ

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Annotation

This article pays great attention to the methods of teaching as well as learning how to make a relevant paragraph in the English language and written according to new technologies.

All differences and advantages of new methods described widely and exactly in this article and the teacher tries to give samples from his experience, which are considered very important for both teachers and learners.

Key words: simple statements, simple structures, non-finite forms of the verb, verb tenses, gerund, infinitive, participles, nouns, singular predicate.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilida tegishli paragraf yaratish va yangi texnologiyalar asosida yozishni o'rganish bilan birga o'qitish usullariga katta e'tibor qaratilgan.

Yangi usullarning barcha farqlari va afzalliklari ushbu maqolada keng va aniq tasvirlangan va o'qituvchi o'z tajribasidan namunalar berishga harakat qiladi, bu ham o'qituvchilar, ham o'quvchilar uchun juda muhim hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sodda gaplar, sodda tuzilmalar, fe'ning cheksiz shakllari, fe'l zamonlari, gerund, infinitiv, kesim, ot, birlik predikat.

Аннотация

В этой статье большое внимание уделяется методам обучения, а также обучению тому, как составить соответствующий абзац на английском языке и написать его в соответствии с новыми технологиями.

Все отличия и преимущества новых методов широко и точно описаны в данной статье, а преподаватель старается привести образцы из своего опыта, которые считаются очень важными как для преподавателей, так и для учащихся.

Ключевые слова: простые высказывания, простые конструкции, неличные формы глагола, времена глагола, герундий, инфинитив, причастия, существительные, сказуемое единственного числа.

Paragraphs are medium-sized units of writing, longer than sentences, but shorter than sections, chapters, or entire works. Because they connect the "small" ideas of individual sentences to a "bigger" idea, paragraph structure is essential to any writing for organization, flow, and comprehension.

Students have a lot of questions when it comes to writing a paragraph: How many sentences should you use? How do you transition within a paragraph? Below we explain everything you need to know about paragraph structure to write like an expert, including several paragraph examples. [6]

How is a paragraph structured?

Understanding the elements of a paragraph is crucial for organizing your thoughts and conveying your message effectively. A well-constructed paragraph typically contains the following elements:

- **Unity:** All sentences in the paragraph should support the main idea stated in the topic sentence. Avoid introducing unrelated ideas that could confuse the reader.
- **Coherence:** The sentences should flow logically and smoothly from one to the next. Use transition words and phrases to help link ideas and maintain readability.
- **Adequate Development:** A paragraph should provide enough detail to thoroughly explain or support the main idea. This may include examples, explanations, facts, or anecdotes.
- **Order:** The information within a paragraph should be organized in a logical sequence. Depending on the purpose, this might be chronological, spatial, or based on importance.

Topic Sentence

The [topic sentence](#) is the first sentence of the paragraph and introduces the main idea. It tells the reader what the paragraph is about and sets the tone for the rest of the sentences.

Supporting Sentences

These sentences develop the main idea introduced in the topic sentence. They provide explanations, examples, evidence, or details to support the topic.

Example:

“When you read a variety of books, you encounter new words in different contexts.”

Concluding Sentence

The concluding sentence wraps up the paragraph by summarizing the main idea or providing a final thought. It gives a sense of closure and helps the reader transition to the next paragraph.

Example: “Therefore, making time for regular reading can significantly enhance language skills.” [7]

Types of paragraphs

Depending on the kind of writing you’re doing, you may need to use different types of paragraphs. Here’s a brief explanation of the common paragraph types most writing deals with.

Expository: Common in nonfiction and all types of essays, expository paragraphs revolve around explaining and discussing a single point or idea.

Persuasive: Just like expository paragraphs, persuasive paragraphs focus on discussing a single point; however, they support opinions instead of facts.

Narrative: When telling a story, a narrative paragraph explains an action or event. Each new sentence furthers or expands upon the action by providing new information.

Descriptive: Also common in storytelling, descriptive paragraphs focus on describing a single topic, such as a person or an environment. Each new sentence adds a new detail about that topic. **Types of paragraphs**

- A **Topic sentence** ought to be followed with justifications.
- **Justifications** are types of sentences serving to prove the main ideas with the help of other sentences.
- Wayne is very shy (*topic sentence*). For example, he finds it difficult to make new friends. **(justification)** [2, b. 43]
My mum is very kind (topic sentence) whenever you meet her, she is busy to help someone. **(justification)**

Paragraph creating can be divided into the following groups.

Paragraph types

gerund infinitive participle noun

GERUND

Gerund is a type of non-finite forms of the verb which has 50% nominal and 50% verbal meaning. Gerund is likely accompanied by nouns in the possessive case or possessive pronouns, Sometimes the action denoted by the gerund is not associated with any doer or any producer of the action. *Living is striving.* [4, b. 193]

The gerund may be used in various syntactic functions. A single gerund occurs but seldom; in most cases we find a gerundial phrase or a gerundial construction.

1. The gerund as a **subject**. **Talking** mends no holes [5, b. 185]

We can use gerund at the beginning of the sentence as a subject which is followed by singular predicate.

- **Reading**(gerund) original texts(distractors) a lot, **leads**(predicate) to enlarge one's vocabulary systematically.
- You can start your body paragraph with gerund using it as a topic sentence.
- *Having been glued on the screen for a long time, (topic sentence) makes his eyes feel tired and consequently he tends to go to bed too late to get up next morning early and in the result he misses attending several lessons on time which leads his name to be in the list of withdrawn students. (justification)*

INFINITIVE

Infinitive is a type of non-finite forms of the verb which has 50% nominal and 50% verbal meaning. The infinitive developed from the verbal noun, which in course of time became verbalized, retaining at the same time some of its nominal properties. Thus in Modern English the infinitive, like the participle and the gerund, has a double nature, nominal and verbal.

1. The nominal character of the infinitive is manifested in its syntactic functions. The infinitive can be used:

- (a) as the **subject** of a sentence.

To go on like this was dangerous. (*Galsworthy*) [5, b. 191]

- **To become** (infinitive) a member of the students' union(distractors) , **demands**(predicate) several urgent document fillings. Talabalar birlashmasiga a'zo bo'lish (uchun) bir nechta to'ldiriladigan xujjatlar talab etiladi.

- You can start your body paragraph with infinitive using it as a topic sentence.

- *To be(infinitive) a skillful tutor, demands a lot of hard work on one's subject.(topic sentence) Furthermore, patience and understanding learners' wish are also essential key aspects of being the best teacher. Therefore, various subjects are taught at institutions specialized to prepare educators. (justifications)*

Mostly gerund and infinitive can be used in different form according to the meaning of the sentences such as: for instance perfect form is usually followed by the prepositions "for" ,"since"

Having lived here for several years, I can find out any street easily.

PARTICIPLES

Participle is a type of non-finite forms of the verb which is both 50% adjective and 50% verb. All the forms of Participle I may be used as an adverbial modifier. Participle I Indefinite expresses an action simultaneous with the action expressed by the finite verb [5, b. 165]

We can use **participles** at the beginning of the sentence by following the clause.

Having lived (participle) in this are for a long time, James can find out any street easily(**clause**).

- You can start your body paragraph with participle using it as a topic sentence.

- *Playing (participle) computer games intermittenly.(topic sentence) He has some problems with his eyes, sometimes clarifying any objet not far from him is likely to seem a bit strange and in the result he has to go to the doctor .(justifications)*

NOUN

Nouns can be used in the prepositional phrase to fulfill various functions. In this case, verifying a singular or a plural predicate seems a bit difficult. Learner sought to clarify the noun standing before the preposition.

- **The importance(noun)** of these remarkable issues, makes (**predicate**) me think deeply.

- You can start your body paragraph with noun using it as a topic sentence.

- The popularity of my hometown, always draws a number of tourists attention to it(**topic sentence**).

- In spite of having myriads of luxury inns, foreigners are often likely to be seen seeking convenience accommodation around the city (**justification**)

All in all, knowing how to make paragraphs like these can increase learners score while being checked in IELTS test. If you use elementary vocabulary in your writing context with above cited structure, it is equalized to the sample which is written with great vocabulary.

simple	paragraph making structure	good vocabulary
If I watch coast views, I don't feel bored	Watching coast views prevents me from feeling bored	In the case of feeling disappointed, I tend to observe coast charming scenery to avoid the situation.

As an ordinary teacher, I would like to stress that each instructor ought to try to encourage their learners by the way as given above and it will show its result in the forthcoming periods.

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